

Studies on Thiazolidinones: Part II

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4-thiazolidinones are prepared directly by condensing 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone, thioglycolic acid, and various amines using benzene as a solvent. The IR spectra indicates the -CO-N and OH group frequency. The compounds have been analysed pharmacologically.

2-METHYL-2-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-3-aryl-4-thiazolidinones with hydroxyl group in the phenyl ring have been reported previously¹. We now report the synthesis, spectra and pharmacological activity of some more thiazolidinones. Thiazolidinones are well known for their anaesthetic², amoebicidal³, hypnotic⁴, and anticonvulsant⁵ properties. It has also been shown to have a deep impact on antithyroid activity with variation in the parent structure⁶. Besides, the presence of N-C-S-bond in a compound has been indicated leading to anti-tubercular⁷, antiradiation⁸, nematocidal⁹ and antifungal activity¹⁰.

2-Methyl-2-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-3-aryl (alkyl or cyclohexyl)-4-thiazolidinones have been prepared by directly condensing the aryl methyl ketone with thioglycolic acid and the respective amine in benzene for 10 hr. The yield of thiazolidinones markedly decreases when the Schiff base has not been isolated first. However, the yield can be increased by adding a pinch of zinc chloride in the reaction mixture.

All the thiazolidinones exhibit a sharp absorption peak between 3000-3200 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of a free hydroxyl group. The hydrogen in these compounds is not bonded through a hydrogen bond to the nitrogen¹³. A strong tertiary amide stretch frequency is also exhibited in the range of 1680 to 1630 cm^{-1} .

Experimental

Preparation of 2-methyl-2-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-3-naphthylthiazolidinones. 2-Hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone¹¹ (0.01 mole) was taken in dry benzene (50 ml). To this was added a solution of α -naphthyl amine (0.01 mole) in dry benzene (25 ml) and thioglycolic acid (0.01 mole) in benzene (10 ml). The contents of the flask were refluxed for 10 hr. Benzene was distilled off, the residue extracted with ether washed with sodium bicarbonate solution (50 ml) and dried (sodium sulphate). On evaporation of ether, the

crude thiazolidinone was obtained which on recrystallisation from ethanol (95%) gave 2-methyl-2-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-3-naphthylthiazolidinone as white granules m.p. 191, yield 50%.

The same experiment was repeated adding a pinch of freshly fused zinc chloride at the initial stage of mixing the reactants. The same thiazolidinone was obtained (compared by TLC) m.p. 191°, and the yield was 62%.

The same experiment was again repeated using *p*-toluene sulphonic acid as a catalyst for the reaction and the yield was 50%.

Other thiazolidinones were prepared with the catalysts and without the catalysts, zinc chloride and it has been concluded that the addition of zinc chloride enhances the yield but *p*-toluene sulphonic acid has no effect on the yield. The compounds are reported in Table 1.

The pharmacological screening

The pharmacological screening of these thiazolidinones was done for anticonvulsant activity by the method of Swinyard¹². The introduction of hydroxyl group increases the LD₅₀ in mice. The compounds were injected intraperitoneally according to standard procedure in gum acacia suspension as they are insoluble in water. Though no compound could give protection against the convulsion produced by electricity, they are found to be mild CNS depressants during the test.

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TABLE I—COMPOUNDS OF THE TYPE

No.	R	Molecular Formula	M.P. °C	LD ₅₀ mg kg	Anticonvulsant activity	Yield% 1	Yield% 2	Required % N	Found % N
1.	α -naphthyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ NO ₂ S	191	> 850	no protection	50	62	4.28	4.30
2.	Cyclohexyl	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ NO ₂ S	155	"	"	49	61	4.77	4.73
3.	2-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ ClNO ₂ S	130	"	"	54	62	4.35	4.06
4.	3-Methylphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ NO ₂ S	155	"	"	57	63	4.65	4.73
5.	Benzyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ NO ₂ S	140	"	"	52	60	4.65	4.54
6.	2-Methylphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ NO ₂ S	120	"	"	50	64	4.65	4.81
7.	n-Butyl	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ NO ₂ S	125	"	"	51	64	5.24	5.47
8.	2-Carboxyphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NO ₄ S	90	"	"	50	63	4.23	4.21

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